

Research

The Impact of Trade between Morocco and China on the Growth of the Moroccan Economy

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Abstract: This paper examines the impact of the Sino-Moroccan trade on the Moroccan economy during the period of 1993-2020 using the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL).

The study uses GDP Per Capita as an indicator of economic growth, and 6 independent variables which are: Moroccan Imports from China, Moroccan Exports to China, Labor force, Gross Capital Formation, Inflation and Real Effective Exchange Rate.

The results indicate that gross capital formation has a positive and significant effect on GDP per capita, whereas inflation has a negative and significant effect.

Real effective exchange rate and Morocco's exports to China both have positive and significant impacts on GDP per capita, whereas imports from China and labor force have positive relationships but insignificant effects on the dependent variable. Specifically, a 1% change in gross capital formation causes a 0.23% increase in GDP per capita, and a 1% increase in inflation leads to a 1.81% decrease in GDP per capita, also a 1% increase in Morocco's exports to China results in a 0.03% increase in GDP per capita. The Morocco imports from China and Labor force have positive relationship but still insignificant effect on the dependent variable.

Keywords: Sino-Moroccan Trade, Export, Imports, ARDL Model, International Trade

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Accepted: 09 April, 2023; **Published:** 13 April, 2023

How to cite this article: Naimi Housame, Wang Jian Feng (2023). *The Impact of Trade between Morocco and China on the Growth of the Moroccan Economy*. *North American Academic Research*, 6(4), 54-64. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7826379>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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1. Introduction

Morocco has been dedicated to a liberalization strategy aimed at boosting economic competitiveness and diversifying its trade partners for a number of decades. The economic climate and allure of the Kingdom have improved as a result of several institutional, legal, and regulatory reforms and the reason for the nation's strong economic development is attributed mainly to these initiatives as well as a supportive international climate.

The diversification of trade partners, particularly with rising powers such as China has become a crucial need in the context of expanding globalization and intensifying trade.

On a bilateral level, Morocco and China have established a strong economic relationship in recent years, with China becoming one of Morocco's leading trade partners. This development is in alignment with the strategic focus of China on the African continent.

The trade between Morocco and China has been growing steadily over the past 28 years and is in line with the strategy of Morocco that aims at diversifying its trading partners, therefore, this study aimed to enrich the empirical literature in this field by examining the impact of trade between Morocco and China on the growth of the Moroccan economy.

2. Literature review on economic growth and international trade

International trade and economic growth are two interdependent concepts that have been the subject of intense academic debate and empirical investigation over the years. The relationship between these two variables has been extensively analyzed by economists, with the aim of establishing the direction of causality, if any, and the nature of the relationship. The question of whether trade can foster economic growth or not is a complex and multi-faceted one, and its answer depends on the country's specific circumstances, the nature of its trade regime, and the stage of its development.

On a theoretical level, Adam Smith (Smith, 1937) asserts in his theory of absolute advantage that with free trade, countries may produce and export goods and services that they can create more effectively than other nations, and buy commodities that they can manufacture less efficiently, such that the assistance benefits all countries.

David Ricardo's theory holds that a nation wins from international trade by exporting goods in which it has the greatest comparative advantage in productivity and importing those in which it has the least comparative advantage, provided a solution to the question of whether international trade benefits nations that have or do not have an absolute advantage in both items (Berkum & Meijl, 1998).

Moreover, the Heckscher Ohlin theory suggests that a country will export goods that use its abundant and cheap factors of production and import goods that use its scarce and expensive factors of production (Heckscher, 1919).

Many nations, particularly least developed countries, are encouraged to pursue export orientation because it promotes specialization, which boosts national output while decreasing domestic price levels. Exports make it easier to utilize the economy's resources to generate products and services, and the surplus may be sold abroad to meet international demand while simultaneously boosting national output and creating foreign exchange earnings that can be used to support economic development (Krueger, 1985).

Imports are the primary channel of capital and technology diffusion since imported foreign technical knowledge has the ability to boost local production levels, and imports also aid in economic exchanges between inhabitants of a country and their external counterparts (Grossman & Helpman, 1993) and (Ram, 1990).

On an empirical level, and the absence of specific studies analyzing the impact of trade between Morocco and China on the growth of the Moroccan economy, this empirical review captured all the possible angles of the actors in this relationship, whether it is the impact of trade between Morocco and other partners on the growth of the Moroccan economy and the impact of trade between China and other partners on their economy.

(Bakari, 2019) investigated the link between economic development, export, and import in Morocco. Empirical study employs VAR modeling approaches and Granger causality. Research suggests that economic expansion benefits exporting. Nevertheless, there is no consequence that goes from export to growth. Moreover, there is no link between imports and economic development.

(El Alaoui, 2015) used yearly time series data for the Moroccan economy from 1980 to 2013 to study the link between export, import, and economic growth. The findings imply bidirectional causation between economic growth and import, unidirectional causality from export to import, and no-directional causality between economic growth and export for short-run causality.

(Bakari & Mabrouki, 2016) investigated the link between economic development, export, and import in Morocco. In empirical study, VAR modeling approaches and Granger causality are applied. The study found a link between economic growth and exports. Research suggests that economic expansion benefits exports. Yet, there is no influence on export growth.

(El Majidi, 2019) used the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) and the error correction technique to analyze the influence of trade openness on economic development in Morocco from 1980 to 2016. The major findings revealed that trade openness has a detrimental impact on both long and short run economic growth volatility.

(Kummer - Noormamode, 2014) conducted a study on growth regressions using panel data econometric models for 37 African nations from 1985 to 2012, revealing that trade with China had a favorable influence on African GDP, but only in the final decade of that era. They also claim that, during this time period, trade with China had a greater influence on African economies than trade with the EU.

3. Model, Data, And Methodology

The hypothesis to be tested in this study is that trade between Morocco and China stimulates economic growth in Morocco. To test this hypothesis, we start with a typical production function as $Y = F(K, L, X)$, where Y is the output or GDP, K is the capital stock, L is the labor force, and X represents other factors that can influence production.

In this case, we can modify the production function to include the specific independent variables of interest:

The multiple regression model and can be expressed as:

$$\text{GDP per capita} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{GCF} + \beta_2 \text{LAB} + \beta_3 \text{MAR EXP} + \beta_4 \text{MAR IMP} + \beta_5 \text{REER} + \beta_6 \text{Inflation} + \varepsilon$$

Where β_0 is the intercept or constant term, β_1 - β_6 are the coefficients or slopes associated with each independent variable, and ε is the error term or residual.

Where: GCF represents Gross Capital Formation, L represents the Labor force, Exports to China represents Moroccan exports to China, Imports from China represents Moroccan imports from China, REER represents Real Effective Exchange Rate, Inflation represents the inflation rate in Morocco.

The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model is used to estimate the relationship between Moroccan GDP per capita and the independent variables of interest.

The sample in this study is a data set of 7 variables, specifically Moroccan GDP per capita and the influencing factors (Moroccan exports to China, Moroccan imports from China, Gross Capital Formation, Labor force, Real Effective Exchange Rate and Inflation) from 1993 to 2020.

The reason for choosing this period is mainly because the availability of the data regarding the trade between Morocco and China and also because the bilateral trade between the two countries started to increase in the 90's.

The data was for Moroccan GDP per capita, Gross Capital Formation, Labor force, Real Effective Exchange Rate and Inflation were collected from the World Bank Database and Moroccan exports to China and Moroccan imports from China were collected from United Nations Comtrade Database

The secondary data obtained were processed using Microsoft Excel and STATA 15 software, then the output results were interpreted descriptively.

4. Interpretation of Tests Results

Dickey-Fuller Test for Unit Root

The Dickey-Fuller test is used to determine if a time series is stationary or not.

Table 1 Dickey-Fuller test results for unit root

	Test Statistic	1% value	Critical value	5% value	Critical value	10% value	Critical value	Stationary
GDP per Capita	3.039	-2.655		-1.950		-1.601		At level
MAR GCF	-2.932	-2.658		-1.950		-1.600		At level
MAR IMP	-3.598	-2.658		-1.950		-1.600		First difference
MAR EXP	4.121	-2.657		-1.950		-1.601		At level
MAR REER	-4.734	-2.657		-1.950		-1.601		First difference
MAR INF	-4.726	-2.655		-1.950		-1.601		At level
MAR LAB	-4.107	-2.655		-1.950		-1.601		At level

Source: Author’s Calculations (STATA 15)

GDP and MAR EXP are non-stationary at the level, while the other four variables (Morocco Imports from China, MAR REER, inflation, and labor force) are stationary either at the level or after taking the first difference. This implies that modeling the relationship between these variables require differencing to ensure stationarity.

Johansen Test for Cointegration

The Johansen test for cointegration is used to determine the number of cointegrating relationships between a set of time series variables. In the output provided, the maximum rank tested is 7, and the tests indicate that there are at least 1 cointegrating relationship between the variables.

Table 2 Johansen test result for cointegration

Johansen tests for cointegration					
Maximum rank	Parm	LL	Eigen value	Trace statistics	5% critical value
0	63	246.5407		287.6841	136.61
1	76	295.70099	0.98041	189.3635	104.94
2	87	326.86633	0.91736	127.0328	77.74
3	96	345.60297	0.77663	89.5595	54.64
4	103	361.91107	0.72873	56.9433	34.55
5	108	377.72926	0.71789	25.3070	18.17
6	111	387.13592	0.52883	6.4936	3.74
7	112	390.38274	0.22875		

Based on the Johansen test, it appears that there is at least one cointegrating relationship between the variables. The exact number of cointegrating relationships is not clear from the output, but it is likely that there are either one or two cointegrating relationships, based on the eigenvalues and trace statistics. These results suggest that the variables in the model are related in the long run and cannot drift too far away from each other.

Correlation Test

The correlation test examines the relationship between pairs of variables.

Table 2 Pearson Correlation Analysis Results

Variables	GDP per capita	MAR INF	MAR GCF	MAR REER	MAR LAB	MAR IMP	MAR EXP
GDP per capita	1.0000	-0.7189	0.1788	-0.0757	-0.0250	0.3003	0.4179
MAR INF	-0.7189	1.0000	0.2526	0.2840	-0.1449	-0.1921	-0.5190
MAR GCF	0.1788	0.2526	1.0000	-0.0116	-0.2677	-0.0835	-0.3334
MAR REER	-0.0757	0.2840	-0.0116	1.0000	0.0579	0.0607	-0.0959
MAR LAB	-0.0250	-0.1449	-0.2677	0.0579	1.0000	0.4123	0.2941
MAR IMP	0.3003	-0.1921	-0.0835	0.0607	0.4123	1.0000	0.53411
MAR EXP	0.4179	-0.5190	-0.3334	-0.0959	0.2941	0.53411	1.0000

The above table demonstrates that the majority of the variables show a positive correlation with one another, therefore if GDP is growing in the same manner, the other variables will also grow. Some of the variable shows negative correlation such as, MAR REER is negative correlate with GDP which indicates that the if MAR REER is growing the GDP will be decreasing, they are the opposite of one other. On the same way inflation is a negative correlation GDP, which imply that if inflation is raises GDP will be lowers.

Multicollinearity Test

To ascertain whether there was a connection between the independent variables in the employed regression model, a multicollinearity test was conducted.

Table 3 Variance inflation factor for multicollinearity test results

Variable	VIF Value	1/VIF Value
dMAR EXP	2.01	0.497248
dMAR IMP	1.65	0.607881
dMAR INF	1.51	0.662473
dMAR LAB	1.29	0.77373
dMAR GCF	1.23	0.815715
dMAR REER	1.12	0.896732
Mean VIF	1.47	

Source: Author’s Calculations (STATA 15)

Based on the results in the table, the highest VIF value is 2.01 for MAR EXP, which indicates that there may be some multicollinearity present with this variable. However, the mean VIF value of 1.47 is below the threshold of 2, indicating that multicollinearity is not a major concern in this model.

The VIF analysis suggests that multicollinearity is not an issue in the regression model.

Autocorrelation Test

Table 4 Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test Results

Breusch-Godfrey LM test for autocorrelation				
Lags(p)	Chi2	df	Prob > chi2	
1	4.076	1	0.0435	
H0: no serial correlation				

Source: Author’s Calculations (STATA 15)

- Null hypothesis: There is no serial correlation.
- Alternative Hypothesis: There is a serial correlation.

Since the p-value is less than the significance level of 0.05, we can reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is evidence of serial correlation in the error term of the regression model.

To address this issue, the autoregressive model will be used to account for the serial correlation in the error terms. The ARDL model allows for the inclusion of lags of the dependent variable, independent variables, and the error term in the regression equation. This helps to capture the short-run dynamics and serial correlation in the error term of the model, allowing for more efficient and accurate estimates of the long-run relationships between the variables.

Heteroskedasticity Test

Table 5 Heteroskedasticity test results

Breusch-Pagan test for heteroskedasticity	
H0: Constant variance	
Variables: fitted values of dgdp per capita	
Chi2(1)	= 0.48
Prob > chi2 =	0.4888

Source: Author’s Calculations (STATA 15)

The table above shows that the chi-squared test statistic is 0.48 with 1 degree of freedom. The associated p-value is 0.4888. Since the p-value is greater than the significance level of 0.05, we fail to reject the null hypothesis of constant variance and conclude that there is no evidence of heteroskedasticity in the regression model.

Stability Test

Table 6 Cumulative Sum (CUSUM) test results

Cumulative sum test for parameter stability				
Sample: 1994 - 2020			Number of observations = 27	
H0: No structural break				
Statistic	Test Statistic	1% Critical Value	5% Critical Value	10% Critical Value
recursive	0.4751	1.1430	0.9479	0.850

Source: Author’s Calculations (STATA 15)

Based on the results of the test, the test statistic of 0.4751 is less than the 1% critical value of 1.1430. This suggests that we do not have sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis of no structural break and conclude that the relationship between the dependent variable and independent variables in the regression model is stable over time.

ARDL Regression Results

ARDL (2,2,2,0,2,0,2) regression

Table 7 ARDL regression results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. error	T	p> t
Cons	-.0008458	.0056471	-0.15	0.004
ADJ				
GDP per capita				
L1.	-1.394352	.1890083	-7.38	0.000
LONG RUN				
MAR GCF				
L1.	.2371158	.0794124	2.99	0.012
MAR IMP				
L1.	.0027992	.0684853	0.04	0.968
MAR EXP				
L1.	.0303591	.0093836	3.24	0.008
MAR REER				
L1.	1.437867	.5682219	2.53	0.028
MAR INF				
L1.	-1.812334	.3400732	-5.33	0.000
MAR LAB				
L1.	.8717723	.8359053	1.04	0.319
SHORT RUN				
MAR INF				
D1.	-1.452406	.2536851	-5.73	0.000
MAR GCF				
D1.	.330623	.0872707	3.79	0.003
MAR IMP				
D1.	.0043122	.0429759	0.10	0.922
LD.	-.0667157	.0379751	-1.76	0.107
MAR REER				
D1.	.379399	.3231583	1.17	0.265
LD.	-1.23753	.3583228	-3.45	0.005
MAR LAB				
D1.	0.005	.4074121	-0.41	0.687
MAR EXP				
D1.	.0423313	.0149507	2.83	0.016
R-squared	0.9831			
Adjusted R-squared	0.9632			

Source: Author's Calculations (STATA 15)

The model has an R-squared value of 0.9831, which means that it can explain about 98.31% of the variation in the dependent variable. This is a very high value, indicating that the model is a good fit for the data.

The F-test of overall significance tests the hypothesis that all the coefficients of the independent variables are jointly equal to zero. A low p-value for this test indicates that at least one of the coefficients is statistically significant. In this case, the p-value is very low (less than 0.05), which means that the overall model is statistically significant.

The adjusted R-squared value is 0.9632, which is still quite high and indicates that the model is a good fit for the data, even after accounting for the number of independent variables.

The Pesaran/Shin/Smith ARDL Bounds Test

The Pesaran/Shin/Smith ARDL Bounds Test is a method for testing the existence of a long-run relationship between two or more variables.

Table 8 The Pesaran/Shin/Smith ARDL Bounds Test

H0: no levels relationship

F-statistic = 20.347 t-statistic = -7.377

		Critical Values (0.1-0.01), F-statistic, Case 3							
		[I_0]	[I_1]	[I_0]	[I_1]	[I_0]	[I_1]	[I_0]	[I_1]
		L_1	L_1	L_05	L_05	L_025	L_025	L_01	L_01
k_6		2.12	3.23	2.45	3.61	2.75	3.99	3.15	4.43

accept if $F < \text{critical value for } I(0) \text{ regressors}$

reject if $F > \text{critical value for } I(1) \text{ regressors}$

Critical Values (0.1-0.01), t-statistic, Case 3

		[I_0]	[I_1]	[I_0]	[I_1]	[I_0]	[I_1]	[I_0]	[I_1]
		L_1	L_1	L_05	L_05	L_025	L_025	L_01	L_01
k_6		-2.57	-4.04	-2.86	-4.38	-3.13	-4.66	-3.43	-4.99

Source: Author’s Calculations (STATA 15)

Since the t-statistic in this case is less than both of these critical values, we reject the null hypothesis of no long-run relationship.

5. Conclusion of The Study

The trade between Morocco and China has been growing steadily over the past 28 years and is in line with the strategy of Morocco that aims to diversify its trading partners. Therefore, this study aimed to enrich the empirical literature in this field by examining the impact of trade between Morocco and China and its impact on the growth of the Moroccan economy, the analysis was based on the econometric analysis of time series in the last 28 years covering the period from 1993 to 2020 , may this study benefit the Moroccan government by providing more information and new insight on the development of strategies that will reinforce the ever growing relationship between Morocco and China. The 1% change in Gross capital formation causes 0.23% increase in GDP Per Capita with standard error 0.7941 and shows significant effect on the dependent variable.

1% increase in Inflation causes 1.81% decrease in GDP Per Capita with standard error 0.34 and shows significant effect on the dependent variable.

1% increase in Reel effective exchange rate causes 1.43% increase in GDP Per Capita with standard error 0.5682 and shows significant effect on the dependent variable.

1% increase in Morocco exports to China causes 0.03% increase in GDP Per Capita with standard error 0.0093 and shows significant effect on the dependent variable.

The Morocco imports from China and Labor force have positive relationship but still insignificant effect on the dependent variable.

An R-Squared value of 0.98 indicates that the variations of the independent variables explain 98% of the variance of the dependent variable under investigation.

Although the trade between Morocco and China has been growing steadily, but there is still room for growth especially for Moroccan exports given that it has a positive impact on the growth of the Moroccan economy, especially that the Chinese market is a huge market and can be compared to a continent and not only to country.

Morocco can also increase its imports from China but imports in machinery and technology that will impact positively the gross capital formation in the country and also ensure a transfer of technology from China to Morocco in order to make the Moroccan firms more productive and competitive on the international market.

Even though through the present Analysis there was no significant relationship between Moroccan imports from China and the growth of the Moroccan economy, nevertheless importing production tools, machinery and technology can impact the level of productivity and efficiency in the country which by its turn will have a positive impact and reinforce the capacity of exporting the Moroccan products internationally, and this by its turn will have a direct and significant impact on the growth of the Moroccan economy and will be in alignment with the findings of this study.

6. Recommendations and Policy Implication

Based on the ARDL model results, the following policy implications and recommendations can be made for the Moroccan government to promote economic growth:

The negative and statistically significant coefficient of Morocco's inflation on GDP per capita suggests that reducing inflation should be a priority. The government can use monetary and fiscal policies to curb inflation, such as adjusting interest rates, implementing price controls, and managing government spending.

The positive coefficient of Morocco's gross capital formation on GDP per capita underscores the importance of investment in physical capital for economic growth. To promote investment in physical capital, the government can prioritize policies that support private investment in infrastructure, equipment, and technology.

The positive coefficient of Morocco's exports to China on GDP per capita suggests that strengthening trade relations with China could have a positive impact on economic growth. To promote exports to China, the Moroccan government can prioritize policies that support export-oriented industries, such as reducing trade barriers and providing export subsidies. Additionally, the government can promote investment in Chinese industries, such as by creating investment incentives for Chinese firms to invest in Morocco.

Although the coefficient of Morocco's labor force on GDP per capita is insignificant, addressing labor market issues can still contribute to economic growth. To improve the productivity and efficiency of the labor force, the government can prioritize policies that support access to education and training programs, reduce the informality of the labor market, and promote entrepreneurship. For example, the government can invest in vocational education and training programs to provide workers with the skills necessary to work in modern industries.

The insignificant coefficient of Morocco's imports from China on GDP per capita suggests that economic diversification can be an important driver of economic growth. To promote economic diversification, the government can prioritize policies that support investment in different sectors of the economy. For example, the government can provide tax

incentives and subsidies for firms to invest in non-traditional industries, such as renewable energy or high-tech manufacturing.

There are also opportunities for the Sino-Moroccan relationship to grow and develop, including the cooperation in Africa, as China and Morocco can work together on shared economic and political interests in Africa, such as infrastructure development, energy and resource management, and political stability.

The future outlook for the Sino-Moroccan relationship is promising even though the Sino-Moroccan relationship is facing challenges, but there are also opportunities for the two countries to work together and strengthen their relationship. The key to success will be finding ways to address the challenges and capitalize on the opportunities for mutual benefit.

The limitations of this study are mainly the study focuses on the impact of trade between Morocco and China on the growth of the Moroccan economy. As a result, this study is unidirectional. Furthermore, the impact of the bilateral trade on the Chinese economy and the Chinese FDI in Morocco will not be covered in this thesis.

The study will focus on a specific time frame, using data from the last 28 years for the period 1993-2020.

The study will focus on the specific set of the following variables, Morocco GDP per capita in annual growth, Morocco Inflation using GDP deflator in annual variation, Morocco Gross capital formation in annual growth, Moroccan Real effective exchange rate in annual growth, Morocco Labor Force in annual growth, Morocco Imports from China in annual growth and Morocco Exports to China in annual growth.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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